

FACTORS AFFECTING YOUTH SPIRITUALITY IN THE MODERN WORLD

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada yoshlar ma'naviyatini yuksaltirishda asosiy omillar hisoblangan, ajdodlarimizning boy tarixiy merosini o'rganish, oiladagi farzand tarbiyasining ahamiyati hamda ta'lim va tarbiyaning dolzarbligi xususida so'z yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Tarixni bilish, ma'naviy meros, o'zlikni anglash, milliy qadriyatlar, oila, tashqi muhit, axborot texnologiyalari.

Annotation: The article talks about the study of the rich historical heritage of our ancestors, the importance of raising children in the family, and the relevance of education and training, which are considered the main factors in raising the spirituality of young people.

Key words: Znanie istorii, dukhovnogo naslediya, self-awareness, natsionalnykh cennostey, semi, vneshney sredy, informatsionnykh tehnologiy.

Аннотация: В статье говорится об изучении богатого исторического наследия наших предков, важности воспитания детей в семье, а также актуальности воспитания и обучения, которые считаются основными факторами повышения духовности молодежи.

Ключевые слова: Знание истории, духовного наследия, самосознания, национальных ценностей, семьи, внешней среды, информационных технологий

Introduction. In the world each one country his own development ways set can because , first of all , his own in the country o` sib coming of young people to the future separately importance giving to him the most important matter as looking will come . now land on the face of countries almost in all , young people education and upbringing the most current topic to be is coming This about in our country young people spiritual in being in the family environment , neighborhood e` tibori , education in the institution there is of possibilities all of them account taken they are for necessary goals and tasks set is being taken and to practice application is being done . Humanity in history his own from the beginning different periods exchange and event - events that he spent all of us good we understand Each period different changes , updates , radical changes , tension with from each other difference by doing came We living period his own productivity , high technologies , information of flow intense the fact that with separately important is rich This period we for a lot positive opportunities to give with one in line , many problems cause is issuing let's say exaggeration ` a it wo n't be . This of course of globalization under the influence happen going on are processes. Globalization process to our lives again fast and deep come in coming - of main factor and reason in particular when speaking that's it objective admit get need - today in the day each which of the state progress and development not only near and long Neighbors , maybe the world scale another region and regions with so closely connected it's going to be something of the country this from the process outside standing positive to the results take not coming to understand , to understand difficult it's not .

In this sense , it is globalization first of all life of their pace incomparable level acceleration means [1;110-111].

Globalization is our opportunity if we emphasize that it increases and accelerates error It won't happen. Which one? our work good quality by doing perform without technology difficult is a task. Why , we are this high to opportunities study closely connected more approaching we are going. This of course us our work high quality , effective the most important the time our savings for comfortable opportunities by creating will give . In our country of young people spiritual and moral upbringing in the system homeland feeling for the motherland faith , patriotism , humanitarianism and national-spiritual values form them own people and of his homeland loyal their children by doing bring up of our country the most higher from the goals one as attention giving is coming . Today's our society development , spirituality formation and society environment main basically as acceptance to do requirement is doing Because of the people life his spirituality with organic depends being a society of morality root the nation history with organic in contact event is considered My in my opinion , humanity of the world great one the illuminator is spirituality there is a light. This is a lamp from others difference that's it of a person consciousness and thinking illuminates his heart and conscience awakens humanity feeling strengthens of Uzbekistan new wake up period to create entered each of us of our compatriot heart and that's how it is in his mind spirituality that's it shine and he us good to work therefore, high responsibility feeling with to live invitation reach necessary For us spirituality - people between mutually trust, respect and attention , people and state the future together to build on the way good aspirations, exemplary qualities is a complex. Otherwise in other words, spirituality is in society all political and social of relationships content and quality defines is the foundation. This foundation how much strong if so, the people and the state as well strong stated that it will be was our country leader Sh.M. Mirziyoyev [2; 248-249]. Indeed , a person from youth forever traditions , different traditions in his mouth to maturity enough In this regard , family , neighborhood, education in their homes spiritual environment harmony , stability important place holds If our ancestors , our ancestors to history look they are mental maturity , spiritual cleanliness , physical strength and Of course , moral to maturity very big attention looking like this individuals ideals in the form of those who saw Among them, Ahmad Fargani , Imam Bukhari , Imam Termizi , Abu Nasr Farobi , Abu Rayhan Beruni , Ibn Sina, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Amir Temur, Mirza Ulugbek , Alisher Navoi like literally our ancestors spirituality symbol that they were us makes you proud , makes you proud . That 's it great from our ancestors one unmatched commander owner Amir Temurni true , courage , bravery , nobility and high spirituality the owner as good we know Amir Temur youth ever since special coaches control under riding , hunting , archery target shooting , other different exercise and military games with busy was and that's it with one in line with science separately engaged . Temur by nature heavy , heavy , deep thoughtful and perceptive and extremely intelligent , in people ability , virtue , especially sincerity quickly understand will receive spirituality mature a person was Peerless determination Courage , bravery and wisdom symbol was this classic figure great kingdom set up statehood about both practical and theoretical heritage left Science , culture , creativity , religion and spirituality development wide road opened [4;129]. We to our ancestors worthy generations being to maturity in our achievement only and only science and craft possession , own upon us relentlessly work to do , spiritual to maturity towards to move forward programming task by

doing we get condition. Times passed, periods series own strength showing the present our day modern information communication without technology imagination by doing It won't happen. Today of our youth most of them main information source as to the internet appeal are doing In the world happening universal changes , economic development in science news inventions of these all public information tools through manifestation that it is happening let's see can People in his life to information demand from day to day increased going , democratic in society public information means TV and radio channels important importance occupation reach with is characterful.

Earth the science of the sphere and technique achievements because of humanity available the same one whole to the part turning around to go globalization of processes to our lives come in coming period with our comparison can Humanity historical progress the same at the time work release of forces development process organize is doing This is the process century after century a thousand years continue reached process is considered. Kurrai the ground a person did not know , he is a leg did not press places didn't stay Science and of technique again - new achievements this about of a person opportunities more increased let's say exaggeration it won't happen . In particular , Islam Karimov own in his works the following emphasizing those who passed Today's in the day modern information in the field actions that's it until tight , that's it until quickly , now as before , yes, it is event from us very far away face gave , his to us relationship carelessly saying no looking it won't happen . That's it to the mood given people or the nation from development face years behind stay leaving it 's nothing . Because it 's today in the day our youth not only study on the platform , but also on radio and television the press and like the internet tools colorful through information and information is taking the world information area again expanded going so one in the circumstances of our children mind only wrapping - unwrapping him do n't read this It's one that you don't see bilaterally education to give their iron wall around with , wrapping get , no undoubtedly , of the time on demand , ours good It is also true to our goals does not come [3; 146].

That's it account received in case present in the day modern technologies land on the face globalization process great accelerating sent Information and spirituality in the fields globalization in the process to himself okay positive and negative aspects are also highlighted .

Modern communication and information technologies, scientific achievements speed with distribution , various of values universal basically harmony, inter-civilizations of communication new quality occupation eco - friendly disasters during mutually help show of possibilities increase naturally , of these to all globalization because of is being achieved . After all, it's tomorrow of our day The essence is basically good pursuit of goals will be it is like the internet in that modern technologies only for good , calm and calm to life service to do need If necessary, this should become the motto of the youth, who are the decisive forces of our tomorrow. It is no secret that globalization in the field of information, while showing many of its positive aspects, also causes a number of problems. This calls for serious attention to the fact that it affects the minds of young people in different ways. The reason is that the majority of today's young people are increasing their worldview and level of knowledge by using technology [2; 87]. Currently, the main national television and radio channels in our country ensure the population's right to impartial and truthful information, increase the cultural level, knowledge and outlook of our compatriots, preserve and develop our ancient traditions, historical heritage, and at the same time, democratic values in the minds of our

citizens. , it should be noted that it is doing a good job in forming a civic position, educating the young generation in the spirit of patriotism and respect for universal values.

In particular, our country faces important tasks in the field of spirituality. The main one of them is to enrich and strengthen our spirituality . In the national consciousness and worldview of our people, which have been formed over the centuries, and in the norms of behavior, a deep respect for parents, the neighborhood community in which one lives, and older people, to the little ones in honor Qualities such as being , showing special respect for the opinion of the team are given priority. Besides , that 's it values our society of spirituality base the stone organize does Because today day our youth in every way mature , intellectual knowledge and potential by doing bring up and most importantly spiritual the world lie down and destroyer from ideas case respectively enrichment rich history of our ancestors their heritage centuries during own value without losing coming training , advice through education in their homes explaining go , modern information of technologies our in our lives place and importance as well only positive from the sides used in the case , spiritual our worldview growing up go , admitting today and development degrees seeing and admitting of the world many developed countries our of our spirituality history How long to periods go that the and great as well as this old from our history for example conclusion released in this case , our youth to spirituality How level attention from being given a tree will give .

National our spirituality develop it our people , especially our youth to his life absorb especially important In particular , spiritual and enlightened young people of our country powerful power and the future are creators . Summary by doing so to speak, human spiritual the world rise different to factors depends. From history people striving for perfection , himself Your Highness show his qualities do it those who started Such qualities in turn honesty and justice , correctness , morality maturity such as input can A child from birth starting from the first spirituality in the family sparks mother milk, family upbringing, ancestors education, homeland feeling through absorbed initially spiritual education right to be given as a result, great to work able perfect a person is brought up . Man identity his ancestors, forefathers who that as much as he knows mother to the country relatively love feeling more rise up keeps going .Today's complicated and intense period problems and difficulties really Spiritual, knowledgeable, own history good who knows his nationality aware , patriotic , enthusiastic, own country from the soul loved only people struggle takes. So it is his own history good knew , to the future hope with every looking people high spiritual to be desire it is necessary.

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